

PACIFICUS

A Literary Magazine (Print & e-Publication)

Volume I, Issue I | A Quarterly Publication

ISSN (Online): 3082-4079 | ISSN (Print): 3082-4060

Publisher: Binas Publishing

Email: binasbookers2013@gmail.com

DR. KRESTER M. DIAZ

Assistant Professor IV

Negros Oriental State University

krestermdiaz@gmail.com

“STYLISTICS IN ACTION: EXPLORING LITERARY LANGUAGE AND MEANING”

Stylistics plays a vital role in understanding and interpreting literature. In the words of Alemu (2015), stylistics deals with a wide range of language varieties and styles that are possible in creating different texts, whether spoken or written, monologue or dialogue, formal or informal, scientific or religious etc.

This exploration aims to reveal the role of stylistics in interpreting literature by using analytical techniques available within the sub-discipline of language study. Though stylistics has been approached from many perspectives, its goal remains the same and that is to negotiate meanings by enabling the readers to make meaningful interpretation of the literary texts and to expand knowledge and awareness of the language in general.

Below is the application of linguistic theories in the analysis of literary texts.

I. Stylistics Analysis on the Linguistics Features with *Interpretations*

"O where are you going?" said reader to rider,
"That valley is fatal when furnaces burn,
Yonder's the midden whose odors will madden,
That gap is the grave where the tall return."

"O do you imagine," said fearer to farer,
"That dusk will delay on your path to the pass,
Your diligent looking discover the lacking
Your footsteps feel from granite to grass?"

"O what was that bird," said horror to hearer,
"Did you see that shape in the twisted trees?"

Behind you swiftly the figure comes softly,
The spot on your skin is a shocking disease?"

"Out of this house" , said rider to reader,
"Yours never will" , said farer to fearer,
"They're looking for you" , said hearer to horror,
As he left them there, as he left them there.
(WH Auden, "O Where Are You Going?")

Lexis

Since poetry creates an avenue for individualized, personalized response in each reader, I would give my subjective interpretation based on the linguistic stylistic features used by the author in the poem *O Where Are You Going?*

On a surface level, this poem is a dialogue between two characters, **a reader** and **a rider, fearer** and **farer, horror** and **hearer**. On a deeper level, it depicts a never-ending battle happening within the human mind and soul, personifying a conversation between the **inner self** and **outer self**. Auden used the lexical words reader, fearer, and horror to mean the inner self while rider, farer, and hearer for the outer self. In the poem, the former lexical items describe the inner self as scared, lazy, and coward to take risks because of the unforeseen innumerable dangers waiting ahead while the latter speaks of courage, boldness, and hope to move forward and conquer the fear of the unknown no matter what struggles and challenges may come his way. Thus, the two groupings connote the stark contrasts between hope and fear, and courage and cowardice.

The inner self (reader) tries to discourage the outer self (rider) from going beyond by describing valley as full of dangers, a place of turmoil, a place where evil spirits, ghostly creatures, and fatal diseases await, and all other dark and deadly metaphors to create horrifying ambience.

Auden also described the footsteps the rider will take as tortuous and twisted from the phrase "granite to grass". This juxtaposition of granite and grass tells of the kind of journey the rider will pass through. It is one way of saying that the rider will experience too much sufferings, hardships, sorrows, and failures which may befall before he reaches the height of success.

Because Auden is known for his archaic style of writing in order to make his piece echo throughout time, he used O as the starter in his first three stanzas which is deliberately archaic (old fashion) along with the words furnaces for chamber and midden for a dung hill though some critics detect sexual references of the two, gap as vagina and midden as anus.

The mentioning of farer in the poem suggests one is going somewhere while the word fearer suggests of being afraid of what is ahead in the voyage. There is also a reference to time of day, 'dusk' which would symbolize the end of a life (death). In the third stanza, bird is mentioned which is very symbolic and would take different interpretations like an omen for instance.

The poem finishes with a repetition of 'as he left them there' which would tell that the rider does not get frightened with what the reader is telling him but courageously takes risks to explore new avenues. Like in life, if you want something, you go for it with no hesitations. You take a risk; you don't always play safe or you'll die wondering.

Grammar

The poem is split into four stanzas with four lines each. The poem started with a question 'O where are you going?' raised by the reader to rider. In the next three lines, the reader gives some pseudo warnings. If you have noticed, the one talking in the next three stanzas is still the inner self. In order to effectively scare or intimidate the rider, scary language is used. Few good examples of this are 'The gap is the grave', 'O what was that bird' and 'Did you see that shape in the twisted trees.'

In the second stanza, Auden used gerunds, looking and lacking, to make the reader feel uneasy about going out of the house. In his last line, there is a grammatical deviation on the use of two

subordinate clauses with no dependent clauses. All the first lines in the three stanzas start with a direct quotation following the exact messages the reader, fearer, and horror try to convey. The last stanza shows the response of the rider, farer, and hearer from all the bad premonitions the other three have on them.

There are also word changes within syntactic category with various word derivations (on a morphological level) / word inflections included. See few examples below.

Free	Bound	Root	Prefix	Suffix
burn	going	going	return	going
imagine	furnaces	furnaces		reader
dusk	odors	odors		madden
delay	trees	trees		looking
granite	softly	softly		lacking
horror	comes	comes		shocking
House	reader	reader		
shape	swiftly	swiftly		
disease	footsteps	footsteps		
path	twisted	twisted		

Mostly, inflections apply to nouns for numbers and possessives like furnaces, trees, and yours; verb to indicate 3rd singular present like comes as well with use of copula be like *That valley is fatal, That gap is the grave, O what was that bird, and The spot on your skin is a shocking disease*; indefiniteness like imagine and discover; and continuous aspects for present participle like going and looking.

Sound (phonetic) Patterns

The poem is in ballad which suggests a form of verse, often a narrative set to music. It is a folk traditional form for the 18th-19th century. It uses quatrain stanzas and quatrain amphibrach tetrameter rhyming which is a metrical unit with unstressed-stressed-unstressed syllables (e.g., remember).

Sound devices and literary devices to create auditory imagery for the readers are being studied in Phonology. Below are the sound devices used in 'O Where Are You Going'.

Alliteration	Consonance	Assonance	Repetition	Rhyme scheme
Reader, rider	Reader, rider	Path, pass	As he left them there, as he left them there.	ABCB
Dusk, delay	Fearer, farer	Spot, shocking		
Spot, skin	Valley, fatal	See, trees		
Twisted, trees	Dusk, pass	Left, left		
Granite, grass	Granite, grass	Reader, rider		
Horror, hearer	Left, left	Them, them		
Diligent, discover	Swiftly, softly	Fearer, farer		
Swiftly, softly	Yonder's, ordors			
Gap, grave	Horror, hearer			
Fatal, furnaces	Midden, madden			
Midden, madden	Looking, lacking			

with which much of his Path, pass	Furnaces, burn			
-----------------------------------	----------------	--	--	--

The language and style used by Auden are very symbolic to his ideology in which much of his poetry circles around moral issues with strong political, social, and psychological context.

Auden is admired by many for his unsurpassed technical virtuosity and ability when writing poems. In fact, as can be seen in the poem analyzed, Auden follows a chronological order from the first stanza to the last. The first three stanzas started with doubts and confusions about what might happen when one takes risks by getting out of his comfort zone. Instead of becoming a prey of his fears and doubts, the last stanza ended on a positive note by making a decision to go out and do more as in the line "As he left them there" which suggests that the rider, farer, and hearer made the final decision to reject the fearing part of his mind and take the challenge to leap into the unknown. It somewhat inspires me as I read the poem because of its powerful message to get up and move beyond that place of hopelessness. It is a 'do or die' decision to make.

The inner turmoil is seen in stanzas 2 and 3 with the use of question marks. Throughout the dialogue between the tension of these two opposite forces, this poem has tried to preach the philosophy of life that man is never created to live depressed, defeated, guilty, condemned, ashamed, or unworthy but created to be victorious.

That is what the outer self has taught me. It helps me realize that I should not fear, for God has not given me a spirit of fear. Somehow the author is successful in echoing his message and that in reaching one's dream, one is allowed to scream, to cry, but not to give up. Sometimes asking validation from anyone won't help. Just listen to your heart. Then choose to be courageous before diving into the obliviousness.